

Bosonic Fields and the Zeta Function – 8T

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Abstract:

By analyzing the new framework that proved bosons isomorphic to prime numbers or one, it is possible to correlate the configuration of the zeta function to propagation of bosonic fields. Such a construction could shade new light on the nature of bosons and might open new areas of research.

Introduction

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \quad (1)$$

$$F_R \# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30:128:850:9254.. \quad (1.1)$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); \quad V \geq 0 \quad (1.11)$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \quad \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); \quad P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

$$8 + (1):(24 + (3)) + 3:(120 + (3)) + 5:(840 + (3)) + 7 \dots \quad (1.12)$$

Recall that the zeta function graph is covering larger and larger area of the real realm for each non-trivial zero calculated. That is synonymous with the fourth representation of the coupling series in which we represent in the form of pi. That was the way to analyze the shape of the electron by replacing the majestic (3) with pi, stating that the photon will propagate from something close to a perfect circle.

$$8 + \left(\frac{\pi}{3} \right) : (24 + (\pi)) + 3 : (120 + (\pi)) + 5 : (840 + (\pi)) + 7 \rightarrow$$

$$8 + \left(\frac{\pi}{3} \right) : (24 + (\pi)) + \pi : (120 + (\pi)) + (\pi + 1.82) : (840 + (\pi)) + (2\pi + 0.716)..$$

So back to the original purpose, to measure the magnitude of a set of bosonic fields at range lower than the electric, we can use the zeta function. Estimating of range could tell us the overall magnitude and by doing so, the relative speed of matter formations in the universe. As each prime is isomorphic to net curvature on the manifold.

The pi representation could also suggest that each bosonic field is propagating over larger and larger areas, similar to non-trivial zeros in the zeta. The third and most obvious uses is to combine the primorial and zeta function in a programming setting, so that for each prime on the critical line there will be a computational result for the coupling magnitude, and so as we mapped the DNA we can also map entire sequence of forces of nature.

Of course, such a construction would never end but we can at least map in order to reach the couplings at the range of gravity in order to understand how many interactions were missed in our analysis and attempts to unify physics. Analysis of that kind could reveal certain forces like the weak, which differ in kind than the rest of the forces, as the bracket inside the parenthesis is not on the prime critical line, and that is why we speculate the left orientation:

There could be more interactions of that sort if we keep developing the series. Such a development of the series using the zeta function for non-trivial zeros may shade light on different kinds of interactions in much faster way or on the distributions of forces that do differ in direction versus those who are not. There could be other uses which are not vivid as to this moment, but recall how much significance the fine structure constant have in physics. For that reason alone, it is worthwhile as one believes, to map all the couplings up to a certain magnitude.

References

- [1] O. Manor. "8 Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)